

Location Extraction from Social Media: Geoparsing, Location Disambiguation and Geotagging

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Definitions

Location – place name (e.g. London), synonymous with the term ‘toponym’, ‘location phrase’ and ‘location mention’.

Geocoding - transform well-formed textual representation of an address into a valid spatial representation (e.g. spatial coordinate).

Geoparsing - does same for unstructured free text and involves location extraction and location disambiguation prior to geocoding.

Geotagging - assigns spatial coordinates to media content items.

Approach

Comparative study among five ‘best of class’ location extraction algorithms for geoparsing and geotagging problems:

- Entity matching using an OpenStreetMap (OSM) database.
- Language model using social media tags and multiple gazetteers.
- DBpedia-based linked-data entity recognition and disambiguation.
- Named entity recognition and GeoNames gazetteer lookup.
- Named entity recognition and the Google Geocoder API.

Results

Geoparse evaluation using over 6,000 manually labelled tweets. Best overall for English and Italian was **map-database** entity matching with (P 0.96 to 0.99, F1 0.90 to 0.97). For Turkish **Im-tags** approach was best (F1 0.66).

Geotagging evaluation for 1km squares using YFCC100m Flickr dataset with over 39,000,000 geotagged Flickr posts. The **Im-tags-gazetteer** approach was strongest (F1@1km 0.49) and showed the strength of using tag sets for location disambiguation.

Application

Geoparsing social media to support breaking news verification with Deutsche Welle [REVEAL project]; Geoparsing online forums to map online illegal plant trade with Kew Gardens and UK Border Force [FloraGuard project]; Geoparsing citizen reports to identify trends and opinions about urban development [CUTLER project].

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